

Performance evaluation and modeling of the ATIR marine current turbine

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Abstract: In this study, the behavior of a platform for tidal energy is analyzed. The turbine of this platform is formed by two counter-rotating rotors aligned with the tidal current, such that one rotor is always under the wake of the upstream rotor. The platform has been tested by towing it with a tugboat to emulate tidal currents. The results of these tests are analyzed in this study, and they are used to validate a model of the turbine. From these results, the control possibilities of the platform generation system are introduced.

Nomenclature

a : axial flow induction factor
 a' : tangential flow induction factor
 c_p : power coefficient
 c_q : torque coefficient
 c_t : thrust coefficient
 v : current speed (m/s)

A : rotor area (m²)
 D : rotor diameter (m)
 R : rotor radius (m)
 P : power (W)
 Q : torque (Nm)
 T : thrust force (N)
 TSR : tip speed ratio

Greek Symbols

β : blade pitch (degrees)
 ω : rotor speed (rad/s)
 ρ : water density (kg/m³)
 η : performance

Subscripts

0 : freestream current
 1 : upstream turbine
 2 : downstream turbine
 a : apparent, it refers to parameters in downstream turbine calculated using freestream (upstream) current speed
 e : effective
 g : generator
 gb : gearbox
 i : number of blade section
 l : losses
 max : maximum value
 r : rotor
 t : tangential
 x : axial
 H : high-speed shaft
 L : low-speed shaft
 P : platform
 ∞ : freestream current

1. Introduction

The tide is defined as the periodic and alternating rise and fall of the waters of the ocean, which is caused by the gravitational attraction of the moon and sun. The cyclical nature of the tidal phenomenon causes the generation of marine currents that vary in direction and intensity during a tidal cycle. One crucial difference concerning other renewable sources is tides are predictable [1], which makes this energy source very attractive.

A floating system called ATIR, which has been developed by Magallanes Renovables, is based on a platform that incorporates a submerged part where rotors are installed [2][3][4]. The platform is designed to be anchored to the sea bottom by four mooring lines, and thus it does not require any construction on the sea bottom. As a consequence, the typical installation and maintenance costs related to marine energy devices can be reduced [4].

The ATIR platform has a horizontal axis tidal current turbine, which appears to be the most mature technology in

tidal energy systems [5][6]. Its turbine is formed by two counter-rotating rotors aligned with the tidal current (from bow to stern or backward), as shown in Figure 1. Both rotors have a variable pitch with a high range of variation, which allows them to change their rotation direction, such that it can harvest energy from the two tide directions without moving the platform.

Historically, counter-rotating rotors are well-known in aviation. Nowadays, modern ships typically use counter-rotating propellers for increased efficiency, because the aft propeller recovers some of the rotational energy in the slipstream from the forward propeller. Additionally, this type of propeller has the capability of balancing the torque reaction from the propulsor, which is an essential aspect of torpedoes and other similar propulsion systems [7].

Counter-rotating rotors have been used in several wind turbine prototypes [8][9][10][11][12]. Nevertheless, there are currently no products mature enough to be commercialized. In tidal energy harvesting, there are few examples of systems that use counter-rotating rotors [13][14][15][16][17]. For

instance, in [14], a turbine formed by two counter-rotating rotors with the same rotation speed is analyzed, and, in [15], a system is demonstrated with two rotors mounted sideways. This kind of configurations can increase the overall power coefficient [13] or reduce the torque over the supporting structure [16][17].

Figure 1: Platform configuration

The platform has been constructed in a shipyard situated at the “Ria de Vigo” in the northwest of Spain, where Magallanes Renovables has its headquarters. In this area, there is not an available site with enough tidal currents to test the platform, so it will be thoroughly tested at the EMEC tidal test site in Scotland (where it is at the time of writing this paper). However, previous to that test, Magallanes made tests to do the setup of the systems to check the correct operation of the platform and its capabilities. For this purpose, the tidal currents were emulated towing the platform using a tugboat [13].

The main focus of this study is on modeling the turbine formed by two counter-rotating rotors by using data collected during tests that took place at the Ria de Vigo (Spain).

The data from tests has been used to parametrize and validate the model of the turbine and the drivetrain. After obtaining the turbine model, the turbine behavior under real tidal conditions is estimated, and different control strategies are proposed.

In the following sections, the ATIR platform and its main components are depicted. Then, the tests conducted are discussed, and their main results are analyzed. Finally, a model of the platform validated using the measured data is introduced. Several control possibilities are also evaluated in this section.

2. Floating Tidal Energy Platform

The tidal energy platform, developed by Magallanes Renovables (Spain) and called ATIR, consists of a floating platform joined to a marine current turbine (MCT) with a double rotor (see Figure 1 and Figure 2). Its main characteristics are shown in Table 1.

The main advantages of being a floating platform are low maintenance (it has an accessible engine room) and a lower installation cost [18]. Because they are floating facilities, they are adaptable to all sea environments and have a low environmental impact.

Table 1: Main characteristics of Magallanes platform

Rated power	1.7 MW
Weight	350 t
Draft/Length/Breadth	25 m / 45 m / 6 m
Rotors	2 (counter-rotating)
Rotor diameter / Separation	19 m / 1 diameter
Rotor rated speed	17 rpm
Pitch	variable (0 to 270°)
Gearbox ratio	98
Generators	2 × 850 kW @ 690 V
Generators rated speed	1600 rpm
Converters	2 × 900 kW AC/AC

Figure 2: Platform launching in the harbor of Vigo

2.1. Turbine configuration

The MCT is formed by a pair of rotors, one at the bow side and the other one at the stern side. Both rotors have three blades and are designed to rotate in opposite directions (see Figure 1). The rotors can vary their blade pitch from 0° to 270°. Therefore, they can optimize the energy capturing under different currents [19], and their rotation direction can be changed according to the tide direction, as shown in Figure 4, thus avoiding the necessity to move the platform.

The rotor hub is 16 m below the sea level (see Table 1). The rotors are aligned with the tide direction, such that when one rotor is upstream with respect to the tidal current direction, the other rotor is downstream.

The rotors are mounted in the same nacelle, which implies a separation of roughly one diameter, such that the downstream rotor is strongly affected by the upstream rotor (see Figure 1).

2.2. Drivetrain

The two rotors have identical drivetrains, each of which consists of a high-speed squirrel cage induction generator (SCIG) [20], which is mechanically coupled to the rotor through a gearbox (see Figure 3). The energy from the generator is delivered to the power network through a full power back-to-back converter. This type of configuration is widely used in European offshore wind farms [20].

Finally, the outputs of the two AC/AC converters are connected to a transformer with four windings, which is shared with the ancillary services. The energy is generated at 690 V and delivered to the distribution network at 11 kV; the medium voltage was selected according to the network conditions at the EMEC site.

Figure 3: Drivetrain configuration

2.3. Clockwise and counterclockwise rotation

The upstream rotor always has clockwise rotation, and the downstream rotor has counterclockwise rotation (see Figure 1). When the current goes to the bow, the bow-rotor is the upstream and the stern-rotor is the downstream rotor. When the direction of the current changes, the blades of the rotors must rotate in opposite directions. The blades must be re-oriented by 180° upon changes in the tide direction.

The rotor blades can rotate by 270° to vary between the flag positions and maximum attack for the two tidal current directions (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Blade pitch positions from feather to optimum pitch position (case I and IV represent feather position, III and VI represent optimum pitch and II, and V represent intermediate positions) for the two tidal current directions.

2.4. Monitoring and control

The platform is monitored and controlled using a SCADA system. In this system, the main variables measured are:

- Marine current speed by means of a current speed meter installed on the hull of the platform
- Platform speed by a GPS (during the towing tests, this value represents the current speed seen by the rotors)

- Torque in the high-speed shaft by means a torque meter (this value is also estimated by the control software of the AC/AC converter)
- Electrical variables (power, voltage, current, ...) through the control software of the AC/AC converter.

Furthermore, during the test, the main variables controlled were:

- Blade pitch position, from 0° to 270°, which allows even changing the rotors' sense of rotation.
- Load torque setting in the AC/AC converter; when this value is zero, the generator is considered to be unloaded. The load torque was set to different values during the tests.

2.5. Power network emulation

During the tests, it was not possible to establish a connection to the power network. Therefore, the network was emulated by means of an autotransformer (400 kVA; 690 V/400 V), a diesel generator (350 kW), and a bank of dump load resistors (600 kW), as shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6. The value of the resistor bank could be adjusted to match the power generated by the platform, such that the consumption of the diesel group could be optimized.

The objective was to maintain the diesel unit generation at the lowest possible value. Therefore, the power injected by the platform had to be matched with the power consumed by the resistors by connecting or disconnecting resistor steps. The system has tested, and the voltage variation satisfied the limits established in European standards [21]. The frequency variation was higher, although the frequency remained within limits allowed by the power converters.

Figure 5: Platform with diesel group and resistor bank on board

Figure 6: Electrical configuration during tests

3. Towing tests

3.1. Test conditions

In this work, the results of the tests in which the tidal current was emulated by towing the platform with a tugboat (see Figure 7 and Table 2) are analyzed. The tests were conducted in the Ria of Vigo (Northwest of Spain) where the seabed is at a depth of approximately 40 m, and was thus not expected to interfere with the platform behavior.

Table 2: Tugboat main characteristics

Draft / Length / Breadth	4 m / 23.4 m / 9.8 m
Gross register tonnage	273 t
Power	3752 HP
Bollard pull	54 t
Avg. Speed	5.7 kn
Max. Speed	11.2 kn

Figure 7: Platform being towed by a tugboat

The main objective of these tests was to configure the platform to work in tide conditions and analyze its behavior. The main differences between these tests and real working conditions under tidal currents are:

- During tides, the current speed decreases with depth [22]; however, the speed profile during towing is almost constant.
- Waves act on the platform and tugboat, thereby limiting the test conditions (speed, towing force, etc.). They induce oscillations in the towing, and thus in the moving speed. It should be noted that the period of the waves seen by the platform is affected by its speed.
- Similar to waves, wind and marine currents affect the test conditions.
- During tests, the towline length is more than 100 m to minimize the impact of the wake produced by the tugboat (see Figure 7).
- The emulated tidal current depends on the tugboat operation; therefore, it is affected by the blade pitch and TSR of the rotors. Under real conditions, the current only depends on the tide.
- The platform showed a certain level of roll, pitch and yaw during towing (see discussion in Section 6).

Several variables were measured during the tests. For example, Figure 8 shows the evolution over time of the following variables:

- GPS Speed (knots): Speed of the platform during the tests. This speed has been used as freestream current speed because, due to the characteristic of the test site, the existing marine current can be neglected.
- Power (kW): Power delivered by the generators of both rotors (no. 1 and no. 2).
- Torque (Nm): Torque of the high-speed shaft of both rotors.
- Blade Pitch (deg.): Blade pitch of the two rotors.

- Rot. Speed (rpm): Rotation speed of the high-speed shaft of both rotors.

The results show that a power of approximately 400 kW was generated during the tests with a platform speed of approximately 5 knots (2.6 m/s). It must be noted that the achievable speed is limited by the capability of the tugboat, which strongly depends on the rotor behavior and sea conditions (waves, wind, etc.).

Figure 8: Evolution over time of several variables during towing tests (blue line: rotor no. 1; red line: rotor no. 2)

3.2. Estimation of feathered and optimum blade pitch positions

After mounting the blades, which was done at sea, it was necessary to check the real values of the blade pitch for the full feather position and the optimum power coefficient.

The blade pitch for the optimum power coefficient is the pitch at which, for a given marine current, the maximum power is generated. It is difficult to obtain because the speed of the tugboat depends on the power produced by the platform. Therefore, for high power values, the tugboat speed is reduced. In any case, this pitch is close to the one at which the rotor speed is maximum under the no-load condition or null power generation (as shown by the simulated rotor behavior in Figure 16). This value must be obtained at a low current speed because it occurs at values of the high tip speed ratio (TSR), and the maximum rated speed of the generator could be exceeded. Accordingly, the optimum pitch position for one rotor can be obtained from tests, as shown in Figure 9 and Figure 7. This value is approximately 7° , which is the mean value of the pitch angle values where the highest power coefficient values at the generator side (c_{pg}) are achieved.

The full feather position refers to that blade position at which the rotor does not rotate at different current speeds. Its value (between 92° and 94°) has been obtained by several tests similar to that shown in Figure 11, where it is registered the pitch angle value at which the rotor starts to rotate.

Figure 9: Blade pitch angle (and power coefficient at the generator side c_{pg}) for different TSR values

Figure 10: Power coefficient at the generator side (c_{pg}) (and blade pitch angle) for different TSR values

Figure 11: Evolution of one rotor from the full feathered position

4. Rotor and Drivetrain Modeling

The main relationship between the power (P_r), torque (Q_r), and thrust (T) in a rotor can be written as [23]:

$$P_r = \frac{1}{2} \rho c_{pr} A v^3; Q_r = \frac{1}{2} \rho c_{qr} A v^2 R; T = \frac{1}{2} \rho c_t A v^2 \quad (1)$$

where A and R are the area and radius of the rotor, respectively; ρ is the fluid density; v is the current speed; and c_{pr} , c_{qr} , and c_t are the power, torque, and thrust coefficients, respectively.

The previous equations can be used when only one rotor is running. However, when the two rotors are working, the running conditions of the upstream rotor (referred as rotor no. 1) affect downstream one (referred as rotor n° 2) due to wake. Furthermore, the current is measured in one point of the platform not affected by the rotor turbulences, so it is considered representative of the freestream current. Accordingly, the parameters of rotor no. 2 are calculated using that current, so they are apparent values. As a consequence, the TSR for both rotors are calculated using the following equations:

$$TSR_1 = \frac{\omega_1 R}{v_\infty} \quad (2)$$

$$TSR_{2a} = \frac{\omega_2 R}{v_\infty} \quad (3)$$

where v_∞ is the freestream current speed in m/s, R is the radius rotor in m, ω_1 and ω_2 are the rotor speed of upstream and downstream rotors in rad/s, respectively, and TSR_1 is the tip speed ratio in rotor no.1 and TSR_{2a} is the apparent TSR value in rotor no. 2. Similarly, the power coefficient in rotor no.1 (c_{pr1}) and the apparent power coefficient in rotor no. 2 (c_{pr2a}) can be defined as:

$$c_{pr1} = \frac{P_{r1}}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A v_\infty^3} \quad (4)$$

$$c_{pr2a} = \frac{P_{r2}}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A v_\infty^3} \quad (5)$$

where P_{r1} and P_{r2} are the power in rotor no.1 and no. 2, respectively. Finally, another parameter of interest is the torque coefficient, so:

$$c_{qr1} = \frac{Q_{r1}}{\frac{1}{2} \rho R A v_\infty^2} \quad (6)$$

$$c_{qr2a} = \frac{Q_{r2}}{\frac{1}{2} \rho R A v_\infty^2} \quad (7)$$

Where Q_{r1} and Q_{r2} are the torque in rotor no.1 and rotor no.2, respectively, c_{qr1} is the torque coefficient in rotor no. 1 and c_{qr2a} is the apparent torque coefficient in rotor no. 2 and R is the rotor radius. Regarding thrust force, it can be defined the thrust coefficient in rotor no.1 (c_{t1}) and the apparent thrust coefficient in rotor no. 2 (c_{t2a}) using:

$$c_{t1} = \frac{T_1}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A v_\infty^2} \quad (8)$$

$$c_{t2a} = \frac{T_2}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A v_\infty^2} \quad (9)$$

being T_1 and T_2 the thrust forces in rotor no. 1 and in rotor no. 2, respectively.

The total power of the platform at the rotor side can be related to a platform power coefficient (c_{prP}) defined as:

$$c_{prP} = c_{pr1} + c_{pr2a} = \frac{P_{r1} + P_{r2}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho A v_{\infty}^3} \quad (10)$$

Apart from power, the total rotor torque over the platform affects the behavior of the platform, e.g., due to its impact on platform roll (see Section 6). It can be related with the torque over each rotor (it must be taken into account that they have counter-rotation) by mean the following expression:

$$c_{qrP} = c_{qr1} - c_{qra} = \frac{Q_{r1} - Q_{r2}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho A v_{\infty}^2} \quad (11)$$

where c_{prP} is the platform torque coefficient at the rotor side.

According to the previous definitions, the performance of the rotor in terms of the maximum torque, maximum power, or minimum thrust is more easily analyzed in terms of the power, torque, and thrust coefficients. Therefore, these coefficients, as previously defined, were used to model the rotor.

The measurement data from the tests were used to obtain values for these coefficients. However, most of the measurements were conducted in the power converter and in the high-speed shaft. As a consequence, to estimate the rotor behavior, it is necessary to consider the performance in terms of the losses in the generators, gearboxes, and AC/AC converters [24], which are modeled in the following sections.

4.1. Gearbox performance

The platform has two gearboxes (see Figure 3) mounted between each rotor (low-speed shaft) and generator (high-speed shaft). The gearbox has a gear ratio of 1:98, and the losses data provided by the manufacturer are shown in Table 3.

From the torque losses at different rotor speeds, the power losses can be obtained. The resulting data were fitted using the following equation (see Figure 12):

$$P_{gbl} = \sqrt{30.5^2 \left(1 - \frac{(30\omega/\pi - 12)^2}{12^2}\right)} \quad (12)$$

where ω is the rotor speed in rad/s, and P_{gbl} are the gearbox power losses in kW.

Table 3: Gearbox characteristics

Rotor speed [rpm]	Losses as input torque [kNm]	Oil sump temperature [%]	Losses [%]
0.2	137.6	-33	12.7
0.3	125.3	-16	11.6
0.4	114.7	-14	10.8
0.7	130.0	-17	12.0
0.7	122.7	-14	11.4
1.4	137.7	-18	12.7
1.4	104.9	-14	9.9
4.2	54.3	-9	5.7
4.2	46.8	-8	5.1
4.5	26.5	14	3.4
8.7	31.5	14	3.8
12.1	24.3	17	3.2
15.6	17.8	18	2.7
17.3	15.0	19	2.5
19.8	13.4	20	2.3
20.0	13.3	30	2.3
20.0	9.3	32	2.0

Figure 12: Power losses in the gearbox

4.2. Generator performance

The platform uses one asynchronous generator for each rotor (see Figure 3), whose data can be seen in Table 4. According to the data from the manufacturer, the generator performance depends on the speed and torque load, as shown in Table 5.

Table 4: Data of generator

Brand	ABB
Type	Asynchronous
Rated Power	850 kW
Rated Torque	5411 Nm
Rated Speed	1500 rpm
Max. Performance	97.9 %

Table 5: Generator power losses in kW

speed [rpm]	Torque/ Rated Torque [%]				
	4%	16%	36%	64%	100%
300	6.3	6.3	6.3	6.3	6.3
600	7.8	7.9	7.9	7.9	8.0
900	9.7	9.7	9.8	10.1	10.9
1200	11.7	11.8	12.2	13.5	16.1
1500	13.9	14.2	15.5	19.1	27.0

4.3. Performance of generator and gearbox

The power available in a rotor can be obtained from the generator power (measured by the AC/AC converter) and the performance values for the generator and gearbox, as follows:

$$P_r = \frac{P_g}{\eta_{gb}\eta_g} \quad (13)$$

where P_r is power in the rotor, P_g is the power in the generator, η_{gb} is the gearbox performance, and η_g is the generator performance. From the power values in rotor and generator and the measurements in marine current, the power coefficient in the rotor (c_{pr}) and the generator (c_{pg}) can be obtained using the following equation:

$$c_{pr} = \frac{c_{pg}}{\eta_{gb}\eta_g} \quad (14)$$

where $P_g = \frac{1}{2}\rho c_{pg} A v_{\infty}^3$.

The power coefficient values shown above have been obtained using the measurements from only the upstream rotor to overcome the influence over the downstream rotor. The values obtained are shown in Figure 13. It should be noted that the tests were conducted at a power lower than the 50% of platform rated power, and accordingly, the rotor speed was also bellow of the 50% of the rated speed. In this

situation, the performance values of the generator and gearbox are approximately equal to 70% and 90%, respectively. The estimated maximum value for the power coefficient at the generator side was about 0.5.

Using the torque values Q_H in the high-speed shaft, where the torque meter is installed, the rotor torque (Q_r) can be obtained from these values and the estimation of the gearbox losses (Q_{gbl}), as follows:

$$Q_r = Q_H + Q_{gbl} \quad (15)$$

where $Q_H = \frac{1}{2} \rho c_{qH} A v_\infty^2$, and c_{qH} is the coefficient torque obtained from the torque at the high-speed shaft. The torque coefficient at rotor (c_{qr}) can be estimated using these data, yielding the values shown in Figure 14, where the maximum estimated value at the generator side is 0.12.

The rotor torque when the generator is running under no load is equal to the gearbox losses plus the no-load losses of the generator. It should be noted that for speeds lower than 1.5 rpm at the low-speed shaft (see Table 3), the gearbox losses lie between 100 and 150 kNm. Nevertheless, other mechanical elements have not been taken into account (e.g., seals and bearings), and thus to start the rotor, a torque higher than 150 kNm would be necessary.

Similarly, the mechanical power at the rotor when the generator is running under no load is the no-load power at the generator plus the power losses at the gearbox. From the measurements, the overall no-load power in the drivetrain is in the range 30–40 kW.

Figure 13: Power coefficient at the rotor side (c_{pr}) and the generator side (c_{pg})

Figure 14 Torque coefficient at rotor side (c_{qr}) and the high-speed shaft side (c_{qH})

4.4. Losses at AC/AC drive

From the measurements (see Figure 15), the converter losses are between 15 and 25 kW for generated power levels up to 340 kW (40% of the rated power) and a generator speed up to 1600 rpm. These values are close to those given by the manufacturer for the relevant running conditions.

Figure 15: Converter power losses vs. power and rotation speed of the generator

4.5. Rotor modeling

From a dimensional analysis of the blades, where 18 blade sections are considered, the rotor was modeled using the blade element momentum (BEM) method [6][25][26] implemented in XFOIL [22][27][28] and Matlab [29]. As a result, curves for the power coefficient (c_p), torque coefficient (c_q) [30], and thrust coefficient (c_t) at different values of the blade pitch, TSR and Reynolds number were obtained as shown in Figure 16, Figure 17, and Figure 18 [31]. These figures show colored contour lines whose numeric values are indicated in the color bars.

As an example of the resulting model, the estimated value for the maximum rotor power coefficient ($c_{pr,max}$) is 0.52 for a

pitch angle of 7° and TSR of 6.8. Under these conditions, the torque coefficient (c_{qr}) is 0.082, and the thrust coefficient (c_{tr}) is 1.1.

The rotor model was validated using measurement data from the upstream rotor and from tests with only one rotor running, so the wake effect between rotors has not to be considered. For this purpose, the coefficients c_{pr} , c_{qr} , and c_t were obtained taking into account the models for the drivetrain components shown in the previous sections. The values obtained from measurements are represented by colored points in Figure 16, Figure 17, and Figure 18), and their values are similar to those in the contour lines of the model.

Figure 16: Values of c_{pr} as function of the TSR and blade pitch

Figure 17: Values of c_{qr} as function of the TSR and blade pitch

Figure 18: Values of c_t as function of the TSR and blade pitch

4.6. Counter-rotating turbine

As mentioned in previous sections, the turbine of the platform is composed of two counter-rotating rotors (the model for a single rotor is shown in Section 4.5) mounted in the same axis and having the same swept area. Depending on the direction of the tide current, while a rotor is upstream (or downstream), the other one is downstream (or upstream). In any case, to analyze the behavior of the complete turbine, the wake effect between rotors has to be considered [11].

By using the model of the upstream rotor, it is calculated the wake effect at a distance of one rotor diameter ($1 \times D$) where the downstream rotor is located (see 10). Once the wake effect is obtained, the rotor behavior of the downstream rotor can be calculated.

During the calculation, it has been considered a set of TSR values from 0 to 15 with a step equal to 0.2 and a set of pitch angles from -5° to 40° with a step of 1° . As a result, it has been solved $3 \cdot 10^6$ working scenarios for the turbine, taking into account that only generating situations have been considered.

As an example of the resulting model, Figure 19 represents the achievable power coefficient values in rotor no. 2 (c_{p2a} as a function of TSR_{2a} and β_2) for different working conditions of rotor no. 1 defined by TSR_1 , β_1 , and c_{p1} .

According to the values shown in Figure 19, when rotor no. 1 is running at its maximum power coefficient, the maximum power coefficient values achievable in rotor no. 2 are lower than 0.03. As an example, this is shown in CASE I with $TSR_1 = 7$ and $\beta_1 \approx \beta_{opt} = 7^\circ$, being β_{opt} the pitch angle where the maximum power coefficient values can be reached. The main reason for this is that the current speed at rotor no. 2 is significantly affected by rotor no. 1. However, when rotor no. 1 is running at higher blade pitch values (see CASE II with $\beta_1 \approx 20^\circ$, $c_{p1} \approx 0.25$), the c_{p2a} value can be up to 0.3. As an example of an extreme situation (see CASE III), the power coefficient of rotor no. 2 can be maximized ($c_{p2a} > 0.5$) for a blade pitch of rotor no. 1 of approximately 20° ($\beta_1 \approx 20^\circ$, $TSR_1 = 5$).

In any case, most of the literature analyzes the wake effect only when the upstream turbine is at its optimum blade pitch, maximum power coefficient, however, the maximum platform power will be achieved when both rotors share the total power [8]. This implies that neither upstream rotor and downstream one will not be working at its optimum pitch, as it will be shown in the following sections.

Figure 19: Achievable c_{pr1} (main figure) and c_{pr2a} (subfigures I to IV) values for different working conditions of rotor no. 1

5. Characterization of the turbine

In this section, the behavior of the turbine of the platform, which is formed by two counter-rotating rotors (see Section 2), is analyzed. First, the influence between the two rotors is analyzed; it must be taken into account that the downstream rotor is always affected by the wake of the upstream rotor. Next, the power, torque, and thrust coefficients are estimated considering this effect. Finally, several considerations of the control possibilities of the turbine are analyzed.

5.1. Considerations of the effect of the upstream rotor on the downstream rotor

Figure 20 shows the TSR for the upstream (TSR_1) and downstream (TSR_{2a}) rotors when the downstream rotor is running under no load. It can be seen that for low blade pitch values (lower than 20°) of the upstream rotor (β_1), the TSR of the downstream rotor (TSR_{2a}) is significantly reduced from 9 to 4. The lowest value is reached when the upstream blade pitch is at its optimum value.

The reduction in the apparent downstream TSR is due to the decrease in the rotor speed. However, the effective reduction could be compensated by the fact that the effective stream current seen by the downstream rotor is also lowered due to the wake effect induced by the upstream rotor.

According to this behavior, during the tests with the constant torque setting in the downstream rotor equal to 1500 Nm, its delivered power is reduced by approximately 17% from 217 to 178 kW when the upstream blade pitch is modified. Meanwhile, the downstream apparent power coefficient (c_{pr2a}) is lowered by about 30% from 0.3 to 0.21 and its TSR (TSR_{2a}) by approximately 20% from 7.5 to 6.

Consequently, it is necessary to consider the simultaneous behavior of the two rotors in order to obtain the turbine model. This will be done in the following section.

Figure 20: Evolution of TSR of upstream (no. 1) and downstream (no. 2) rotors under blade pitch variations with downstream generator running under no load

5.2. Power coefficient of upstream and downstream rotors and platform power coefficient

The maximum generation of the platform is achieved when, for a given marine current, the total power extracted by the two rotors reaches its maximum value. This situation can be evaluated using the platform power coefficient (c_{prP}) (see Eq. 10) that takes into account the overall energy extracted by the two rotors under certain marine current conditions.

The power coefficient of a turbine formed by two rotors is usually higher than the coefficient of a turbine formed by a single rotor. However, the advantages of this configuration are more closely related to other running characteristics, such as torque balancing [10][32][33]. In this section, the values of the platform power, torque, and thrust coefficients will be estimated, and the estimated values will be compared with the results obtained during the tests.

As mentioned above, the behavior of rotor no. 2 is affected by rotor no. 1. Figure 21 shows the power coefficient (c_{p1}) of rotor no. 1. For every running condition of rotor no. 1 (i.e., TSR_1 and β_1), the maximum achievable power coefficient of rotor no. 2 ($c_{p2a,max}$) and its corresponding running conditions (TSR_{2a} and β_2) are obtained, as presented in Figure 22 and Figure 23. According to this procedure, the platform power coefficient ($c_{prP} = c_{pr1} + c_{pr2a,max}$) can be obtained as shown in Figure 24. As can be seen, the maximum platform power coefficients are easily achieved when the upstream rotor operates at pitch angles higher than the optimum one [11].

Under those conditions, the platform torque coefficient difference ($c_{qrP} = c_{qr1} - c_{qr2}$) represents the torque balance

between the rotors (see Figure 25). Similarly, the thrust coefficient sum represents the overall thrust of the platform (see Figure 26).

In the figures mentioned above, a set of points (#1 to #5) is represented as an example, which were obtained from the measurements and whose values are shown in Table 6. There is a reasonable agreement between the measured and estimated values. Furthermore, it can be seen that the maximum platform coefficient can be obtained in a wide range of working conditions of rotors no. 1 and no. 2, which allows the design of different control strategies.

Table 6: TSR and c_p values obtained from measurements during tests

#	TSR_1	β_1 (°)	c_{pr1}	TSR_2	β_2 (°)	$c_{pr2a,max}$	$c_{prP} = c_{pr1} + c_{pr2a,max}$
1	5.25	15.32	0.26	4.85	6.61	0.25	0.51
2	5.40	15.31	0.27	4.91	6.59	0.25	0.51
3	5.99	11.12	0.36	3.93	7.70	0.15	0.51
4	6.42	11.12	0.36	3.80	7.70	0.14	0.50
5	8.06	7.20	0.45	3.40	7.57	0.06	0.51

Figure 21: Power coefficient in rotor no. 1 (c_{p1}) (values obtained from measurement are included as points marked with #)

Figure 22: TSR values of rotor no. 2 (TSR_{2a}) that maximize apparent power coefficient of rotor no. 2 ($c_{p2a,max}$) for given working conditions of rotor no. 1 (values obtained from measurement are included as points marked with #)

Figure 23: Blade pitch values of rotor no. 2 (β_2) that maximize apparent power coefficient of rotor no. 2 ($c_{p2a,max}$) for given working conditions of rotor no. 1 (values obtained from measurement are included as points marked with #)

Figure 24: Maximum platform power coefficient values ($C_{p1} + C_{p2max}$) for given working conditions of rotor no. 1 (values obtained from measurement are included as points marked with #)

Figure 25: Torque coefficient difference ($C_{q1} - C_{q2a}$) for given working conditions of rotor no. 1 and for maximum power coefficient (C_{p2max}) of rotor no. 2 (values obtained from measurement are included as points marked with #)

Figure 26: Thrust coefficient sum ($C_{t1} + C_{t2}$) for given working conditions of rotor no. 1 and for maximum power coefficient

(C_{p2max}) of rotor no. 2 (values obtained from measurement are included as points marked with #)

5.3. Considerations of the control strategy of the platform

As shown in the previous section, for a given stream current, it is possible to achieve a platform power coefficient of approximately 0.5 (see Figure 24). This value can be reached under different running conditions of rotors no. 1 and no. 2 (see Table 6).

In this context, it is possible to maximize the power delivered by the platform and simultaneously achieve another objective. For example, in order to minimize the roll of the platform, it would be desirable that both rotors have a similar torque, considering that they have counter-rotation. The torque can be supposed as balanced when both torque coefficients are similar.

As an example, Table 7 shows the running values estimated for point #2 in Table 6. The platform power coefficient is close to 0.5, and the torque coefficients of rotors no.1 and no. 2 (C_{qr1} and C_{qr2a}) are quite similar.

Table 7: Running values for point #2

	Rotor no. 1		Rotor no. 2		Total	
TSR_1	5.40	TSR_{2a}	4.91			
β_1 (°)	15.31	β_2 (°)	6.59			
C_{pr1}	0.27	$C_{pr2a,max}$	0.22	$C_{pr1} + C_{pr2a,max}$		0.49
C_{q1}	0.050	C_{q2a}	0.045	$C_{q1} - C_{q2a}$		0.005
C_{t1}	0.35	C_{t2a}	0.56	$C_{t1} + C_{t2a}$		0.91

6. Roll, pitch, and yaw during the towing test

When the platform is operating, the torque of the rotor produces the roll of the platform. This roll is related to the torque of the rotor and the metacentric height due to the positions of the centers of buoyancy and gravity (see Figure 27).

The ATIR platform has two counter-rotating rotors, and, when they have the same torque, the roll of the platform is canceled. When they do not have the same torque, the roll is a function of the torque difference between the rotors. When towed, the platform roll causes a misalignment of the traction forces, which induces significant pitch and yaw (see Figure 28). Figure 29 shows different roll values during a test when only one rotor was running; in this case, the relationship between generator torque and roll is clear.

Figure 27: Roll, pitch, and yaw of platform associated with torques in upstream (upper) and downstream (lower) rotors

Apart from mechanical stress on the platform, the roll, pitch, and yaw affect the generation of the turbine (e.g., the effective area seen by the current is reduced when the rotor axis is misaligned with the marine current) or the towing effectiveness (e.g., the towing resistance of the platform is higher when the yaw increases).

The platform pitch is corrected by moving water between reservoir tanks placed in the stern and bow. However, this could affect the position of the center of gravity and, therefore, the overall platform behavior.

All of the abovementioned aspects must be considered when extrapolating the towing tests to real tidal current conditions.

Figure 28: Roll and yaw of ATIR platform during tests with only one turbine running

Figure 29: Roll values during tests

7. Conclusions

The ATIR platform is a tidal energy device, whose turbine is formed by two counter-rotating underwater rotors aligned with the tidal current. In this paper, it is presented an analysis of this platform based on test results and a complete model for its generation system.

The starting point for this study is the results of the tests carried out at the Ría de Vigo (Spain). During those tests, the platform was towed to emulate the tidal currents. In those conditions, the platform was operated in the same way that under real tidal currents, although with reduced rated power due to the size of dump loads.

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, a complete model for the generation systems has been developed. It includes the following elements:

- Losses in gearboxes, generators, and AC/AC converters.
- Using BEM techniques, the rotor behavior in terms of the TSR, blade pitch, and power coefficient has been estimated. The torque and thrust coefficients have also been obtained.
- The wake effect of the upstream rotor on the downstream rotor.

Model tuning has been done using real data from the above-mentioned tests.

Once the model is obtained, the performance of the platform in terms of the power coefficient has been estimated. An approximate value of 0.5 for the MCT has been achieved during tests. Also, the model allows analyzing the torque balance between rotors, which affects the platform roll, and the thrust forces by means its corresponding coefficients.

Furthermore, the behavior of the ATIR platform under different conditions than those during tests was analyzed. It has been concluded that the use of aligned dual rotors allows operation under a wide range of running conditions while the platform power coefficient is close to its optimum value. In this context, several control strategies can be established, e.g., to compensate the roll of the platform by balancing the torque in rotors.

As a result, the paper presents a model for a full-scale prototype of a tidal energy platform. This model has been used to analyze the behavior of the platform in terms of energy production, torque and thrust. Furthermore, the

viability of control strategies with multiple objectives (energy, platform stability...) has been studied.

8. Acknowledgment

This work is part of the project OCEAN_2G which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°730628.

9. References

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10. Appendix: Wake effect modeling

In order to analyze the behavior of the complete turbine, it must be considered the fact that the rotors are aligned with the tide current. So, the downstream rotor, that can be the stern or bow rotor depending on tide direction, is under the wake of the upstream rotor. This usually approximated as an effective reduction of the current speed [34][35][36][37], however, due to the proximity of the two rotors (see Table 1) more detailed model has to be used. That model has to take into account the wake rotation [19][38][39][40], i.e., the axial and tangential current speeds induced by the wake in the downstream rotor [11][41][42].

If only a rotor is considered, the axial speed ($v_{x,i}$) and the tangential speed ($v_{t,i}$) provoked downstream by the rotor blade section i at a distance equal to $l \times D$ is [11]:

$$\frac{v_{x,i}}{v_{\infty}} = 1 - 2a_i \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{v_{t,i}}{\omega r_i} = 2a'_i \quad (17)$$

where r_i is the radius of the rotor blade section i in m, ω is the rotor speed in rad/s, and, finally, a_i and a'_i are the axial and tangential flow induction factors in m/s, respectively. When the downstream rotor is considered, axial and tangential speed in that rotor can be written as [42]:

$$\frac{v_{x,i}}{v_{\infty}} = 1 - a_i \left(1 + \frac{2x}{D} \left(1 + \frac{4x^2}{D^2} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{v_{t,i}}{\omega r_i} = a'_i \left(1 + \frac{2x}{D} \left(1 + \frac{4x^2}{D^2} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \quad (19)$$

where x is the distance to the downstream rotor, for the ATIR platform $x = D$.

Using the above equations, axial and tangential speed on the downstream rotor can be obtained, as shown in Figure 30 and Figure 31 where these speeds have been calculated for different rotor distances ($1D$ and $2D$). To get those speeds, the running conditions shown in Table 8 have been considered.

Table 8: Running conditions for wake calculation

Rotor	Parameter	Value
-	Free stream current speed (v_{∞})	1 m/s
1	Pitch angle (β_1)	17°
1	TSR (TSR_1)	5.2
1	Rotor Speed (ω_1)	5.67 rpm
2	Pitch angle (β_2)	13°
2	TSR (TSR_{2a})	4.3
2	Rotor Speed (ω_2)	4.19 rpm

Figure 30 Axial speed (v_x) in a downstream rotor when it is located at a distance $1D$ (left) and $2D$ (right)

Figure 31 Tangential speed (v_t) in a downstream rotor when it is located at a distance $1D$ (left) and $2D$ (right)

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